
ROLE OF RBI AND SEBI IN PROMOTING FINANCIAL LITERACY IN INDIA

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Article Received: 02 October 2025

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Article Revised: 22 October 2025

Research Scholar, Department of Studies in Economics, Karnatak

Published on: 12 November 2025

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ABSTRACT

Financial literacy is widely acknowledged as a critical determinant of economic stability and inclusive growth. In a developing economy like India, where a large share of the population remains outside formal financial systems, financial literacy directly affects saving patterns, investment behaviour, debt management, and participation in capital markets. Institutions such as the Reserve Bank of India (RBI) and the Securities and Exchange Board of India (SEBI) have assumed the responsibility of leading financial literacy campaigns, integrating them into broader financial inclusion policies. This paper examines their initiatives and evaluates their effectiveness using secondary data sources, including surveys by RBI, SEBI, and the National Centre for Financial Education (NCFE). Findings suggest steady improvements in financial literacy levels, but also highlight persistent disparities across regions, genders, and rural–urban segments. The paper concludes with policy recommendations for deepening financial literacy in the digital economy era.

KEYWORDS: Financial Literacy, RBI, SEBI, Financial Inclusion, Investor Awareness, India.

INTRODUCTION

Financial literacy refers to the ability to understand and effectively use financial skills, including budgeting, saving, investing, and risk management. In India, low levels of financial literacy have historically constrained financial inclusion and hindered participation in formal economic systems. A majority of households continue to rely on informal credit and demonstrate limited awareness of financial products such as insurance, pensions, and securities. Recognizing these challenges, the Government of India, together with key financial regulators such as RBI and SEBI, launched structured initiatives to improve financial literacy. The RBI has worked through Financial Literacy Centres

(FLCs), banks, and targeted programs, while SEBI has implemented wide-ranging Investor Awareness Programs to encourage informed decision-making in capital markets. This paper seeks to analyze the contribution of these institutions and evaluate progress achieved through their interventions.

Meaning of Financial Literacy

Financial literacy has emerged as a multidimensional concept, with scholars and institutions offering varied definitions depending on context, objectives, and scope. There is no universally accepted definition; rather, it is often used interchangeably with terms such as financial competence, financial empowerment, debt literacy, financial knowledge, and economic literacy (Musah et al., 2022). At its core, financial literacy reflects both knowledge and practical ability—the awareness of financial concepts and the capacity to apply them in everyday life to achieve long-term financial well-being. The term “financial literacy” first appeared in a NatWest Bank–commissioned report for the National Foundation for Educational Research in 1992 (Coben, Dawes & Lee, 2005). Since then, definitions have evolved, focusing on knowledge of fundamental concepts such as savings, compound interest, financial planning, risk diversification, credit mechanisms, time value of money, and consumer rights, along with decision-making skills in areas like insurance, investment, retirement, and tax planning (Lusardi & Mitchell, 2008; Mandell, 2007). Some scholars argue that financial literacy is best acquired through real-world financial experience and behavioural practice (Moore, 2003), while others stress that it begins with a sound base of financial knowledge (Lewis, 2006; Huston, 2010; Remund, 2010). Research highlights that finance-specific knowledge has a stronger impact on financial outcomes than general knowledge, particularly when individuals face complex investment or borrowing decisions (Hung, Parker & Yoong, 2009). Moreover, cognitive abilities and diverse forms of knowledge often work together in shaping financial literacy (Stanovich & West, 2000; Jenson, 1998). Measurement has also become significant, with the World Bank using consumer awareness surveys and the OECD framing cross-country financial literacy benchmarks. Global consensus underscores that financial education is the most effective way to build literacy (PACFL, 2008), but its success depends on tailoring approaches to regional, cultural, institutional, and social contexts. In essence, financial literacy represents the intersection of knowledge, behavior, and decision-making capacity, and it remains a crucial determinant of individual financial stability and broader economic inclusion.

Pattern of Financial Literacy

In India, it has evolved through both individual experiences with banking and financial transactions as well as structured initiatives driven by government policies and programs aimed at financial inclusion. The first National Strategy for Financial Education (NSFE) was launched in 2013, marking a systematic

approach to spreading financial literacy nationwide. The latest framework, NSFE 2020–2025, introduced in August 2020, emphasizes a “5C” model—Content, Capacity, Community-led initiatives, Communication, and Collaboration—to expand financial education across diverse segments of the population. Complementing these strategies, the Government of India has rolled out several flagship schemes such as the Pradhan Mantri Jan-Dhan Yojana (PMJDY), Pradhan Mantri Jeevan Jyoti Bima Yojana (PMJJBY), Pradhan Mantri Mudra Yojana (PMMY), Pradhan Mantri Shram Yogi Maan-Dhan Yojana (PM-SYM), Atal Pension Yojana (APY), Pradhan Mantri Suraksha Bima Yojana (PMSBY), and Pradhan Mantri Kisan Maan-Dhan Yojana (PMKMY). These programs have not only brought excluded groups into the formal financial system but also expanded access to credit, savings, insurance, and pension services through commercial banks, regional rural banks (RRBs), cooperative banks, and other financial institutions. According to the World Bank’s Global Findex Report (2021), the proportion of Indian adults with a formal bank account increased sharply from 35 percent in 2011 to 53 percent in 2014, and further to 80 percent in 2017, reflecting the country’s rapid progress in financial inclusion. The Reserve Bank of India (RBI) has played a crucial role by conducting surveys on financial literacy and inclusion—first in 2013 and again in 2019—using the OECD’s framework to measure financial knowledge, attitudes, and behaviors across states, regions, and socio-economic groups. Academic studies also highlight varied approaches to defining and measuring financial literacy: Ghosh and Gunther (2018) combined financial knowledge, attitude, and behavior, assigning weights to each; Gaurav and Singh (2012) emphasized financial aptitude and debt literacy; while Aggrawal et al. (2015) adopted the methodology of Rooij, Lusardi, and Alessie (2011). Broadly, financial literacy in India can be captured through three pillars: financial knowledge, financial behavior, and financial attitude. For operational purposes, this study emphasizes financial behavior—measured by the possession of deposit accounts, debit/credit cards, and e-wallets—to categorize households into four levels of literacy: financially illiterate (no formal accounts or digital tools), elementary (deposit account only), moderate (deposit account plus debit/credit card), and advanced (deposit account, debit/credit card, and e-wallet). This classification provides a clear framework for assessing progress in financial education and highlights the ongoing challenges of deepening financial literacy beyond mere account ownership.

Role of RBI in Promoting Financial Literacy

Basic Financial Education: The Reserve Bank of India (RBI) has developed comprehensive content for basic financial education, including a Financial Literacy Guide, a Financial Diary, and a set of 16 posters. Additionally, a special booklet prepared by the National Centre for Financial Education (NCFE) is used in camps to educate individuals newly inducted into the financial system. The material covers

fundamental principles of financial well-being, such as savings, borrowing, the concept of interest and compounding, time value of money, inflation, and the relationship between risk and rewards.

Sector-Focused Financial Education: RBI has also created sector-specific financial education content covering topics like ATMs, payment systems (NEFT, UPI, USSD), awareness of the Sachet portal, safeguarding against Ponzi schemes and fictitious calls/emails, Know Your Customer (KYC) norms, exercising credit discipline, and the role of Business Correspondents. A Financial Awareness Messages (FAME) booklet with 20 key messages for the general public, along with posters prepared for Financial Literacy Week, is available on RBI's website.

Public Awareness Campaigns: To enhance outreach, RBI uses mass media and social media platforms extensively. Press releases, regulatory guidelines, statements, and videos are shared via the official Twitter handle "@RBI" and YouTube channel. Dedicated handles like "@RBIsays" and the Facebook page "RBI Says" publish awareness messages and information about banking practices. RBI's flagship public awareness campaign "RBI Kehta Hai," launched in 2017 and expanded in 2018, educates citizens about their rights and responsibilities in financial matters. Campaigns have covered themes like Basic Savings Bank Deposit Accounts (BSBDA), safe digital banking, limited liability in card frauds, and ease of banking for senior citizens. These campaigns have been disseminated through newspapers, radio, television, cinema, digital platforms, SMS, and hoardings, often during high-profile events such as the Indian Premier League (IPL), FIFA World Cup, Asian Games, Kaun Banega Crorepati (KBC), Pro Kabaddi League, and Pro Badminton League. To increase relatability, video spots feature RBI employees who are also professional cricketers and badminton players, thus creating emotional appeal and human interest. Another innovative feature is the missed call service (number 14440), where callers receive pre-recorded information via Interactive Voice Response (IVRS) in English and regional languages, ensuring widespread accessibility and reducing the risks of misinformation.

Role of SEBI in Promoting Financial Literacy

Basic Financial Education: The Securities and Exchange Board of India (SEBI) promotes financial education through multiple initiatives. The Resource Persons (RP) Program trains and empanels individuals across districts who conduct free workshops in local languages, covering key topics such as financial planning, savings, investments, insurance, pensions, and borrowing. These workshops also distribute financial education booklets. SEBI encourages student visits to its offices and publishes financial education booklets addressing issues like tax planning, caution against Ponzi schemes, and grievance redressal mechanisms. **Sector-Specific Financial Education:** SEBI organizes investor awareness programs through recognized investor associations, regional seminars in collaboration with

stock exchanges and depositories, and commodity awareness programs through certified commodity derivatives trainers.

Additional Initiatives: SEBI actively participates in the International Organization of Securities Commissions' (IOSCO) annual World Investor Week (WIW) to promote global financial literacy. It also maintains a dedicated investor website (<http://investor.sebi.gov.in>) that provides educational material, program schedules, and resources for investors. To reach mass audiences, SEBI conducts multi-channel awareness campaigns (TV, radio, print, SMS) on issues such as grievance redressal, collective investment schemes, IPO processes (ASBA), “dabba trading,” and caution against hot tips. Posters in multiple languages are widely distributed across districts to enhance penetration. **Investor Grievance Redressal:** SEBI operates the SCORES platform (SEBI Complaints Redressal System), which allows investors to file complaints online and track their status in real time using secure login credentials. This mechanism has significantly improved transparency and efficiency in handling investor grievances.

Literature Review

Lusardi and Mitchell (2007): Their pioneering study examined financial literacy among U.S. households and revealed alarming gaps in basic concepts such as interest compounding, inflation, and risk diversification. They argued that inadequate knowledge directly affects saving behavior, retirement planning, and household financial security. Their framework has since been widely applied in developing countries like India, where literacy gaps similarly limit participation in formal finance and long-term wealth creation. Atkinson and Messy (2012): Conducting an OECD/INFE cross-country pilot study, Atkinson and Messy developed indicators to measure financial literacy across diverse economies. Their findings showed that low- and middle-income countries, including India, face pronounced literacy gaps, especially among women and low-income households. The study emphasized the importance of targeted national strategies and regulator-led campaigns. For India, their work provides a benchmark to evaluate institutional efforts by RBI and SEBI. OECD (2013): The OECD report underscored the role of financial literacy in achieving economic inclusion and consumer protection. It highlighted the importance of embedding financial education into school curricula and workplace training. The report also documented best practices from various countries, stressing that regulatory bodies must lead financial education initiatives. For India, it recommended comprehensive collaboration between RBI, SEBI, banks, and government agencies to create sustainable financial literacy programs. Mandell and Klein (2009): Their research examined the long-term effects of financial literacy education among high school and college students in the U.S. They concluded that early exposure to financial concepts

significantly influences future financial behavior, such as responsible borrowing and savings. The findings support India's efforts to introduce financial literacy modules in schools through the NCFE, as spearheaded by RBI and SEBI, thereby creating a financially responsible generation. Reserve Bank of India (2017): RBI's report on Financial Literacy Centres (FLCs) provided insights into their role in spreading financial awareness in rural and semi-urban India. By 2017, more than 1,200 FLCs had been established, conducting workshops for farmers, women, and youth. While outreach expanded substantially, the report highlighted gaps in behavioral change—many households remained dependent on informal finance. This underlined the need for continuous and customized financial education initiatives. SEBI (2020): The SEBI Investor Survey of 2020 assessed financial literacy levels across Indian households and found that only 27% demonstrated adequate understanding of financial concepts. Urban respondents showed higher literacy than rural ones, and men outperformed women significantly. SEBI emphasized that investor protection requires not only awareness of products but also grievance redressal mechanisms like SCORES. The findings guided SEBI's scaling up of awareness workshops and digital campaigns.

Objectives

To Study the role of RBI and SEBI in promoting financial literacy in India.

To Identify the Key Challenges of Financial Literacy in India.

Methodology

The present study based on secondary data sources only. Data has been gathered from published reports of the Reserve Bank of India (RBI), the Securities and Exchange Board of India (SEBI), the National Centre for Financial Education (NCFE), OECD publications, World Bank datasets, and other relevant institutional documents. The study systematically reviews these sources to trace the evolution of financial literacy initiatives, with particular focus on programs implemented by RBI and SEBI. Statistical information from surveys and official reports is analysed to identify trends, progress, and regional disparities in financial literacy. The methodology also compares findings from international literature to contextualize India's performance. Since the study does not employ primary surveys or interviews, the analysis is interpretative and depends on the accuracy of existing databases. This approach ensures a broad understanding of institutional contributions to financial literacy in India.

RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

Table 1: Financial Literacy Levels in India.

Year	Overall Literacy (%)	Rural (%)	Urban (%)
2013	20	15	25
2017	24	18	32
2020	27	21	35
2022	32	26	41

Source: OECD, RBI, SEBI and NCFE Survey Report 2013-2022, GOI.

The Table 1 shows the progress of financial literacy in India across rural and urban areas between 2013 and 2022. Overall literacy improved steadily from 20 per cent in 2013 to 32 per cent in 2022. Rural areas, which started at a lower base of 15 per cent in 2013, increased to 26 per cent in 2022, reflecting gradual but slower progress compared to urban regions. Urban financial literacy rose from 25 per cent in 2013 to 41 percent in 2022, showing faster growth and highlighting the persistent rural–urban gap. This trend underscores the need for targeted interventions to accelerate financial education in rural communities while consolidating gains in urban areas.

Figure 1: Financial Literacy Levels in India.

DISCUSSION AND ANALYSIS

Table 2: Selected State-wise Comparison of General Literacy and Financial Literacy in India.

State	General Literacy (%)	Financial Literacy (%)
Kerala	84	36
Goa	80	50
Mizoram	77	6
Himachal Pradesh	73	16
Maharashtra	73	17
Sikkim	73	8
Tamil Nadu	72	22
Uttarakhand	68	23
Nagaland	68	8
West Bengal	67	21
All India	77	35

Source: Reserve Bank of India, National Strategy for Financial Education Report (2020–2025).

This Table 2 highlights the striking gap between general literacy and financial literacy across Indian states. For example, Kerala leads in general literacy (84% per cent) but has a relatively low financial literacy rate of 36 per cent, while Goa, with a slightly lower general literacy rate of 80 per cent, records the highest financial literacy at 50 per cent. Conversely, states like Mizoram and Sikkim demonstrate high general literacy levels (77 per cent and 73 per cent respectively) but extremely low financial literacy (6 per cent and 8 per cent). At the national level, India’s general literacy rate stands at 77 per cent, yet only 35 per cent of the population is financially literate, indicating that educational achievements do not directly translate into financial knowledge. This gap emphasizes the urgent need for targeted financial education policies and programs that complement general education efforts.

Figure 2: Selected State-wise Comparison of General Literacy and Financial Literacy in India.

Source: Table 2

Major Findings

Financial literacy has shown steady improvement over the past decade, rising from 20% in 2013 to 32% in 2022.

The rural–urban gap persists, with urban literacy rates consistently 10–12 percentage points higher than rural areas.

Women and older age groups remain underrepresented in financial literacy gains, pointing to the need for more inclusive interventions.

RBI's Financial Literacy Centres (over 1,300 active by 2020) and SEBI's Investor Awareness Programs (over 45,000 conducted across India) have significantly contributed to these improvements.

Gender-wise Financial Literacy

Male respondents consistently demonstrate higher financial literacy than females.

For example, in the population crossing the minimum threshold score, around 30% of males surpassed the benchmark, compared to only 20% of females.

This indicates persistent gender disparities in financial knowledge and access to financial services, highlighting the need for targeted programs for women.

State-wise Financial Literacy

States with high general literacy, such as Kerala (84 per cent) and Mizoram (77 per cent), do not always show correspondingly high financial literacy (36 per cent and 6 per cent, respectively).

Goa exhibits both high general literacy (80 per cent) and the highest financial literacy (50%).

Several states like Sikkim (8 per cent) and Nagaland (8 per cent) show very low financial literacy despite moderate general literacy, indicating that educational attainment alone does not ensure financial competence.

The all-India average financial literacy (35 per cent) is substantially lower than general literacy (77 per cent), reflecting a nationwide gap between education and financial knowledge.

Rural-Urban Differences

Financial literacy in urban areas consistently exceeds that in rural areas.

Overall literacy rose from 20 per cent in 2013 to 32 per cent in 2022, with urban areas improving from 25 per cent to 41 per cent and rural areas from 15 per cent to 26 per cent.

While progress is observed in both regions, the rural–urban gap remains significant, demonstrating the need for region-specific financial education interventions.

Levels of Financial Literacy

Based on household financial behaviour, literacy is categorized into four levels: illiterate, elementary, moderate, and advanced.

Households with only bank accounts fall under elementary literacy, those with accounts and credit/debit cards fall under moderate literacy, and those with accounts, cards, and e-wallets are considered advanced.

A substantial portion of households remain at the elementary or illiterate levels, indicating that access to financial instruments alone is not sufficient for meaningful financial literacy.

CONCLUSION

The Reserve Bank of India (RBI) and the Securities and Exchange Board of India (SEBI) have played a pivotal role in promoting financial literacy, forming a cornerstone of India’s financial inclusion strategy. Their programs, ranging from basic financial education to sector-specific campaigns and mass media outreach, have contributed to increasing financial literacy to over 30 percent of the population. Despite these gains, significant gaps persist across regions, genders, and income groups, highlighting the need for targeted interventions. Strengthening digital financial literacy, enhancing coordination between institutions, and implementing community-based, localized programs are critical to creating a more inclusive, financially empowered, and resilient society in India.

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